

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure S1: Maximum Likelihood phylogeny of *Gobiiformes*. Nodes are supported at 100% bootstrap except as indicated with circles at nodes. Black = 95-99% bootstrap; Grey = 75-95% bootstrap; Light grey = 50-75% bootstrap. No nodes were supported at <50% bootstrap.

Figure S2: ASTRAL tree of *Gobiiformes*. Nodes are supported at 100% local posterior probability (LPP) except as indicated with circles at nodes. Black = 95-99% LPP; Grey = 75-95% LPP; Light grey = 50-75% LPP; White = <50% LPP.

Figure S3: ML phylogeny of *Gobiiformes* with branches shaded in accordance with gene concordance factors (gCF), from low (red) to high (green).

Figure S4: ML phylogeny of *Gobiiformes* with branches shaded in accordance with site concordance factors (sCF), from low (red) to high (green).

Figure S5: Scatterplots showing the relationships between (a) bootstrap vs. branch length; (b) sCF vs. gCF; (c) gCF vs. branch length; (d) sCF vs. branch length, for branches of the *Gobioidei* phylogeny. Dots are colored in accordance with bootstrap values, and branches with low bootstrap, gCF, and sCF are circled. Circles in (a) are labeled with their phylogenetic position: blue dots represent nodes among the backbone divergences within *Gobiidae*, green and yellow

dots represent branches among species of *Amblygobius*, *Hypseleotris*, *Bathygobius*, or Atlantic *Apogonidae*. The branches subtending *Gobiidae*, *Oxudercidae*, and the *Gobiidae-Oxudercidae* clade receive moderate support and are indicated on all plots.

Figure S6: Representative results of TESS-CoMET analyses of stochastically resolved (TACT) completely sampled trees of *Gobioidei*. 34% recovered the pattern shown in (A), with increases in speciation and extinction rates around 55 Ma at the origin of *Gobioidei*. The pattern in (B), with a shift around the mid-Miocene, was recovered in 33% of replicates; the pattern in (C), high speciation and extinction rates throughout the history of *Gobioidei*, was recovered in 22% of replicates, and the pattern in (D), with a shift in speciation and extinction rates around 34 Ma at the Eocene-Oligocene transition, was recovered in 11% of replicates. 73% of replicates supported ($BF > 2$) the presence of a mass extinction in the Miocene.

Figure S7: Placement of fossil calibrations on the phylogenetic tree of *Gobiiformes*. Details of the fossil calibrations are given in the Extended Materials and Methods, Supplementary File S4.